

I wanna dance with somebody

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Software

- [SORSE](#)
- [Event Website](#)

Category: talks

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1 The Carpentries, US

The Carpentries vision is to be the leading inclusive community teaching data and coding skills. Our first lesson program, Software Carpentry, was founded on several core values, including feedback, gratitude, and collaboration. The role research and data plays in your personal and professional life may contribute to your personal values and confidence in working with data. Have you ever considered your journey to data, your personal values, and whether they align? During this talk we will explore your personal journey to data and research, all while contemplating the following: **How do your personal values align with your work as a Research Software Engineer?** This talk is a pulse check. Be prepared to take notes, dig deep, and wrestle with issues of equity, inclusion, and accessibility.